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ISSN 2961-1695 (Print)
ISSN 2961-1997 (Online)

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Compliance of Building Code in Construction of Residential Buildings in Sisne Rural Municipality, Rukum (East) District

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Abstract- Nepal is in the earthquake-prone country where 80% of housing belongs to informal construction. Informal construction rarely follows building codes. All local levels have legal obligation to implement Nepal National Building Code. However, the newly formed municipalities and especially rural municipalities face challenges in enforcing building codes.

The objective of this study is to determine the Compliance of Building Code in Construction of Residential Buildings in Sisne Rural Municipality, Rukum (East) District, to determine the characteristics, awareness and capabilities of masons involved in building construction and to determine the reasons behind the non-compliance of building code in construction and their probable solutions to overcome. The methodology involved was field observation, questionnaire surveys, and Key Informant Interview (KII).

The study showed that the out of 27 constructed buildings only one building was comply with the checklist of compliance and remaining buildings are not complied. Similarly, out of 13 under construction buildings, none of the buildings are comply as per the compliance checklist. Various parameters like changes in plinth area, size of room, change in depth of beam and change in size and position of staircase have been altered than approved design and drawings. Similarly, lapping of column rebar, lapping of beam rebar are major lacking in under construction buildings. There is a lack of sufficient awareness levels of the masons on basic concept behind the compliance of the building code working in the construction buildings they are not fully capable to implement and follow during construction. Majority of mason's perspective for the reasons behind non-compliance of building code is due to instructions from owner during construction. Masons too alter the drawings to make easy in construction violating the compliance requirement.

Lastly, it has been found that the major reasons behind non-compliance in construction are due to lack of awareness of general public and house owner on code compliance as this is very new subject to them, lack of

sufficient training to technical manpower in the municipality for timely and frequent supervision, lack of availability of trained masons and contractor in Sisne Rural Municipality, lack of effective process of building permit and standard operating procedures for controlling code compliance during construction, lack of coordination between the house owner, designer and masons involved in construction, misconception of the house owner that the compliance of code will increase the cost of the building, lack of sufficient practical knowledge among sub-engineers and lack of stringent monitoring and supervision and disbelief of house owners.

The study recommends the probable solutions to overcome the problems of non-compliance as conduction of mass awareness programme on need of earthquake resistant design and application of building code for the general public and house owner, sufficient training to their in-house technical personnel, municipality should start to train the available mason in Sisne Rural Municipality, prepare and enact standard operating procedures for effective building permit process to enhance the code compliance during construction, introducing three party agreement processes between the owner, designer and mason involved in the construction for better coordination, prepare and enact effective reward and punishment system for compliance and non-compliance through stringent monitoring and supervision during construction.

Keywords: Building Code, Compliance, Rural Municipality, Awareness, Capabilities, RC Building.

I. INTRODUCTION

Nepal is located in the highly seismically active zone. Nepal was placed at the eleven-top earthquake vulnerable countries in the world, paralleled as sitting on a time-bomb. Kathmandu, the capital city, is considered as one of the most vulnerable cities in the world; and is being put on a red alert. Even though the Reinforced Concrete (RC) construction was started in early 1980s, engineered construction was only felt

after enforcement of building codes in 2006 and almost 70 % of existing RC buildings are either owner-built constructions constructed with the help of contractors following by-laws or constructed as per the mandatory rules of thumbs as suggested by Nepal Building Code (Gautam, et al., 2016).

The bulk of buildings are constructed informally; rough estimates indicate that over 80% of housing is informal. There is very little or no application of building codes in informal sector construction. Even in the very small proportion of formal sector housing, adherence to building codes are generally lacking or limited at best. Bangladesh and Nepal have building codes, but enforcement and compliance face significant challenges; the codes serve mainly as good practice guidelines. It is up to professionals, builders or authorities to follow those (Bhattarai & Kumar, 2017).

Earthquakes are thus a relatively frequent and disastrous natural event in Nepal, and a major earthquake is likely in near future. The earthquake disaster risk of urban areas in Nepal, especially the capital area of Kathmandu Valley, is ever increasing alarmingly due to rapid urbanization, poor construction practice, and lack of disaster preparedness (Chaulagain, et al., 2015). "Earthquake alone does not kill people; it is the non-engineered buildings that kills, i.e., the collapse man-made structure do. (Bhattarai & Kumar, 2017).

Much of the damage to more than half a million residential structures in Nepal may be attributed to the prevalence of owner-built or owner-supervised construction and the lack of owner and builder responsiveness to seismic risk and training in the appropriate means of complying with the NNBC (Gautam, et al., 2016).

The devastating Gorkha Earthquake measuring to 7.6 ml having the epicenter occurred near Barpak village of Gorkha district which is 181 km northwest of Kathmandu on 25 April 2015. The earthquakes destroyed 604,930 houses completely and 288,856 houses were partially damaged. Mostly, old, non-engineered, adobe and masonry buildings collapsed and/or were severely damaged by the earthquake. In addition, some engineered buildings also damaged or collapsed due to poor workmanship and quality of construction materials (Subedi & Poudyal, 2019). It is evident that earthquakes do not kill people; rather the weak structures kill the people. If we stay in a well-constructed earthquake resistant building and the

surroundings, we can live safely even in an earthquake prone area.

Due to lack of proper implementation of by-laws, MRT and other buildings codes along with poor construction monitoring mechanism, many structures in urban areas are found to be haphazardly constructed and piled up, such structures have enhanced the vulnerability, so it is direly needed to reframe the construction monitoring mechanism along with monitoring of ongoing changes in structures in terms of non-structural members. The common construction practice was found to be more adhered towards strong column and weak beam framework for owner-built constructions in Nepal, so it would be crucial to enforce the building codes, ductile detailing and proper development length as well as anchorage strategies onwards (Gautam, et al., 2016).

A case study in Karyavinayak Municipality shows that out of the total registered buildings drawing, 78% of the buildings were of class C Building that can be detailed as per Nepal Building Code (NBC):205 while the rest 22% of building were of Class B Building that require detail analysis and design accordingly. Most of the building of both classes have ductility related problems like stirrups spacing, anchorage of bars, number of bars in column, detailing in staircase and bar diameter. Also, the configuration related problems like short columns effect, columns not in grid lines, and discontinuous beam were commonly observed during field survey (Chaulagain, et al., 2015).

(Dixit, 2013) In "Challenges of Building Code Implementation in Nepal" states that building construction process for residential buildings in Kathmandu Valley are constructed by their owners.

II. STATEMENT OF PROBLEM

Construction practice has been one of the major highlights of our civilization. Stone and mud mortar buildings were the major structures to be built in the rural area of Nepal. But with the development in civilization construction practices has been shifted towards the use of cement mortar and rebar. Rukum (East) district has not left untouched from this modernization in constructional practice. So, in order to adopt the safe and earthquake resistant construction practice Sisne Rural Municipality of Rukum (East) District, has also set the rules to pass the building drawing with Reinforced Concrete (RC) frame structure before construction. The municipal engineer's check the compliance of drawing and the

construction at three different stage namely temporary construction permit (up to plinth level), permanent construction permit (after completion of construction up to plinth area) and final completion certificate after the completion of buildings. So, this research has been developed to know the compliance status of NNBC and drawing with construction

III. RESEACRH OBJECTIVE

- a) To study about the status of building code compliance in construction of residential building in Sisne Rural Municipality.
- b) To assess the awareness, and experiences of construction contractor/masons towards building code compliance in construction of residential building in Sisne Rural Municipality.
- c) To find out the reasons behind lacking of construction compliance and to trace out the probable best suggestions for the implementation of Construction Compliance in Residential Building in Sisne Rural Municipality.

IV. METHODOLOGY

A. Research Design

This research aims to study the construction compliance of residential building with design, reasons for not following the construction compliance, non-compliance parameter and best possible suggestions for the implementation of construction compliance in residential building at Sisne Rural Municipality, Rukum (East) District.

B. Research Approach

The study consists of qualitative research approach for analysis. The information was collected using Literature review, Field Survey and Collection of data, Questionnaire survey, KII, Data entry, analysis, and interpretation, Research report with findings and conclusion.

C. Study Area

The study area of the proposed research work is *Sisne Rural Municipality* as a whole, which is in Lumbini Province of Nepal

D. Study Population, Sample Size

Sisne Rural Municipality had set for the registration and Permission to Build Reinforced Concrete Buildings Since fiscal year 2074/75. A study conducted in this Rural Municipality showed that around 40 RC frame Structure residential buildings has requested for permission to construct the building. Therefore, all 40 buildings were considered as a population from which all buildings were consider for the analysis as a sample size. Among 40 permitted buildings for construction 27 buildings were completed and remaining 13 buildings are under construction.

Table 4.1. List of Population and Sample

S.N.	Respondent types	Number of Population	Sample
1.	Total Permitted Building	40	40
1a.	Completed Buildings	27	27
1b.	Buildings under construction	13	13
2.	Local Contractor/Masons of buildings under construction	13	13
3.	Municipal Elected Officials (Chairperson, Vice-chairperson)	2	2
4.	Municipal Administrative and Technical Personnel	8	1
5.	Municipal Administrative Officer	1	1

E. Primary and Secondary Data Collection

i. PRIMARY DATA ARE COLLECTED BY:

a. Field Verification: A site investigation of sampled buildings was done and compliance was checked based on the checklist prepared. The checklist involves:

- Location of Building
- Characteristics of mason
- Configuration related parameter
- Strength related parameter
- Ductility related parameter
- Connection related parameter
- Causes of non-compliance

b. Questionnaires: A set of different questionnaires were prepared for local contractor/mason. The questionnaires were related to assessing the awareness, perspective, and capabilities of the mason to construct the buildings to comply with the provision of building code.

c. KII – Key Informant Interviews (KII) were conducted with the chairperson, vice chairperson, chief administrative officer and technical personnel of Rural Municipality who are involved in building permit related works in the municipality. The unstructured interviewing method was used. The KII was conducted asking the reasons behind the non-compliance and probable solutions to overcome it.

ii. *SECONDARY DATA COLLECTION*

Secondary Data are collected from Municipal Records, Approved Drawings and Design, Building Permit Certificate Photographs, Relevant textbooks, Prevalent acts and regulations, Published and unpublished literature, journals, and reports, Records of the related government offices, Online search mediums such as science direct, research gate, sci-hub, Google scholar, etc., and previously conducted research.

F. Research Matrix Table:

Based upon the plinth area of permitted building 28 buildings have plinth area less than 1000 Sq. ft. “Category C” and 12 buildings have plinth area more than 1000 Sq. ft. “Category B”. Following table 4-2 shows the detail plinth area in Sisne Rural Municipality. Analyzing the building design drawings submitted for the construction permit in Sisne Rural Municipality, 100% buildings have followed the standard of Nepal National Building

To assess the awareness, and experiences of construction contractor/masons towards building code compliance in construction of residential building in Sisne Rural Municipality .	Awareness, perspective, and capabilities of construction contractor/masons measured in Academic qualification, experience, relevant trainings	Primary Data collected via questionnaire	Descriptive statistics such as percentage, charts	Awareness level of the Local contractor/Mason in complying building code while construction
To find out the reasons behind lacking construction compliance and to trace out the probable best suggestions for the implementation of Construction Compliance in Residential Building in Sisne Rural Municipality	Reasons behind non-compliance and its probable solutions	Primary Data collected via KII	Narrative statement	View of Sisne Rural Municipality representatives for effective building code implementation and compliance

<i>Objectives</i>	<i>Data Required</i>	<i>Source of Data</i>	<i>Tools</i>	<i>Outcomes</i>
To study about the status of building code compliance in construction of residential building in Sisne Rural Municipality.	The data of different parameters of building Code as per the prepared checklist in residential buildings of Sisne Rural Municipality	Field observation and measurement, checklist, Approved drawings & building permits/certificates, building codes, Municipal records, legal and other relative documents,	Descriptive statistics such as percentage, charts	Compliance of individual parameters and total compliance.

V. RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

A. **General Information**

Rate of RC frame building construction in Sisne Rural Municipality has been found in increasing order. After the formation of Rural Municipality in 2017, all together of 40 RC framed building owners have filed application for the registration process. Out of 40 buildings, 27 buildings have completed its construction process and 13 buildings are under construction.

The average size of building (in term of number of floor) was found to be 2.88 whereas 52.5 % of the owners have taken permission for the construction of 3 floor building slightly higher than average size. More than two third owners who had taken construction permission have preferred less than 3 stories building falling under the category of Part II. These buildings are generally comfortable to travel without the use of lift and are most common type of RC Frame building constructed across the country (DUDBC, 2015).

Based upon the plinth area of permitted building 28 buildings have plinth area less than 1000 Sq. ft. "Category C" and 12 buildings have plinth area more than 1000 Sq. ft. "Category B". Following table 4-2 shows the detail plinth area in Sisne Rural Municipality.

Analyzing the building design drawings submitted for the construction permit in Sisne Rural Municipality, 100% buildings have followed the standard of Nepal National Building

B. **Building Code Compliance in Constructed Buildings**

Among 27 buildings which are completed in construction are considered for building code compliance. The checklists for the constructed building in field verification are Check for Column Size and Grid Position, Check for Beam Size and Grid Position, Check for Plinth Area of The Building, Check for Room Size and Orientation, Check for Staircase Size and Position, & Check for Final Built-Up Area

C. **Building Code Compliance in Under Construction Buildings**

13 under-construction buildings have been observed and verified through a compliance checklist for the code compliance. The major parameters considered for the checklist survey are: Depth and Construction of foundation, Column size and position, Beam size and position, Floor Slab thickness, Clear cover, Reinforcement detailing, Stirrups and Sill and lintel bands in construction.

D. **Building Code Compliance in Under Construction Buildings**

13 under-construction buildings have been observed and verified through a compliance checklist for the code compliance. The major parameters considered for the checklist survey are: Depth and Construction of foundation, Column size and position, Beam size and position, Floor Slab thickness, Clear cover, Reinforcement detailing, Stirrups and Sill and lintel bands in construction.

S.N.	Description of compliance parameters	Compliance (%)	Non-Compliance (%)	Remarks
1	Depth of Excavation in foundation	100	-	Observed on buildings constructed up to Plinth level.
2	Foundation Construction			
a	Size	100	-	Studied on buildings constructed up to Plinth level.
b	Rebar placement and Size	100	-	Studied on buildings constructed up to Plinth level.
c	Strap beam	100	-	Studied on buildings constructed up to Plinth level.
3	Column Size and Position	100	-	Studied on all ongoing buildings
4	Beam Size and Position			
a	Tie beam	100	-	Studied on foundation Construction building
b	Plinth Beam	100	-	Studied on buildings constructed up to Plinth level.
c	Floor Beam	77.78	22.22	Studied on 1 st , 2 nd and final completion buildings
5	Slab Thickness			
a	Floor Slab	100	-	Studied on 1 st , 2 nd and final completion buildings
b	Staircase Slab	77.78	22.22	Studied on 1 st , 2 nd and final completion buildings
6	Reinforcement detailing			
a	Foundation	100	-	Studied on foundation construction building
b	Column	100	-	Studied on buildings except final completion stage
c	Beam	100	-	Studied on 1 st , and 2 nd floor constructed building
d	Slab	100	-	Studied on 1 st , and 2 nd floor constructed building
e	Staircase Slab	100	-	Studied on 1 st , and 2 nd floor constructed building
7	Stirrups	100	-	Studied on buildings except final completion stage
8	Lapping Position of Bar			
a	Column	-	100	Studied on buildings except final completion stage
b	Beam Top Bar	71.42	28.57	Studied on 1 st , and 2 nd floor constructed building
c	Beam Bottom Bar	71.42	28.57	Studied on 1 st , and 2 nd floor constructed building
9	Sill and Lintel Band	85.71	14.28	Studied on 1 st , and 2 nd floor constructed building

Discussions:

During field measurement and study of under construction buildings the major non-compliance parameters identified were, lapping position of bar in column, lapping position of bar in top and bottom beam, thickness of members.

Lapping of rebar on Column and Beam

Another major non-compliance identified during this study was lapping of rebar on column. 100% building failed to comply. Similarly lapping position of top and bottom rebar of beam was also found another non-compliance parameter. 28% of buildings failed for proper lapping of rebar on top and bottom of beam.

The reasons behind this noncompliance are due to lack of proper training on reinforcement detailing, mason failed to understand the importance of varying the lapping position.

Another reason for this non-compliance is due to lack of technical visit from Rural Municipality.

Slab thickness of staircase

During field study it has been found that almost 23% of the building whose construction is ongoing failed to meet this compliance. Slab thickness of buildings has been casted more than design which could have been result of improper laying of formworks and lack of workmanship of mason involved in construction.

Depth of Beam

Another major non-compliance identified during the study was variation on the size of beam depth. Almost 16% of the buildings have been found with the changes in the dimensions of beam. This has been found while measuring the beam after concreting. This non-compliance parameter was due to improper size casing of columns and improper placement of formworks.

Reinforcement Size, Stirrups, and reinforcement detailing

100% buildings under study have followed the design parameters and placed the rebar size properly.

Stirrups size selection on buildings was also found satisfactory. 100% of the buildings have used proper size stirrups for the construction of column, beam and slabs. Masons and owner have not changed the size of rebar but lapping of rebar was found to be major non-compliance.

Sill and Lintel Band

During field observation, it has been found that only one building has not provisioned the sill and lintel band during construction as per the design and drawings.

E. Characteristics, Awareness and Capabilities of Construction Contractor/Masons

a) Experience, Relevant training and Academic Qualification of Masons

The detailed experience of lead mason involved in under-construction buildings in Sisne Rural Municipality. More than 80% of the lead masons involved the ongoing constructions of Sisne Rural Municipality have more 5 years' experience in construction field.

The study shows that 100% mason who are involved in building construction are not trained professionals. For the formal training mason have to travel to dang and Butwal which seems to be difficult for mason. Another reason for 100% non-trained mason was none of the recognized institution had initiated for organizing formal trainings.

To understand the educational status of lead mason involved in ongoing constructional works of Sisne Rural Municipality a questionnaire survey was conducted. The academic levels of the lead mason have direct impact on understanding of detail constructional drawings of buildings.

Approximately 38.46% of total lead mason were found literate whereas another 38.46% of lead masons had not completed school leaving certificate level. Only 23.08% lead masons had completed school leaving certificate level.

b) Level of Awareness of Construction Contractor/Mason

A questionnaire survey was conducted to study the level of awareness of the local contractor/mason who is involved in ongoing construction site. The basic questions stated as follows were asked.

TABLE 5.1
General Awareness of Mason

Description	% of No	% of Yes
General Concept on Earthquake and its Phenomena	69.23	30.76
General Concept on Earthquake Resistant Design and Construction	76.92	23.08
General Concept on Building Code and its Provisions	84.61	15.38
General Concept on Approval Process of Drawings from Municipality	53.84	46.15

The study shows that awareness levels of the masons under consideration have not sufficient level of awareness on basic concept behind the compliance of the building code.

c) Capabilities of Construction Contractor/Mason

A questionnaire survey was conducted to assess the existing capabilities of construction contractor/mason who is involved in ongoing construction site. The basic questions stated as follows were asked to measure the existing capabilities.

The responses are detailed out in the following table.

Table 5.2
Capabilities of Mason

Description	% of No	% of Yes
To Follow Earthquake Resistant Construction	76.92	23.07
To Read the Architectural and Structural Drawings and Detailing	84.61	15.38
To Understand the Material and Its Test Specification	84.61	23.07
To Understand the Construction Methodology	69.23	30.76

The above results show that lack of education of lead mason be one of the major causes for not following the construction compliance of RC Frame buildings.

d) Perspective of Mason towards Non-Compliance

A questionnaire survey was conducted to trace the perspective of masons for the reasons behind non-compliance of building code in construction practice. 69.23% of the lead masons answered that the compliance of building code has been violated during construction due to instructions from owners. Whereas, it has been found that 15.38% of masons have alter the drawings make the work easy violating the building code compliance. Only 15.38% of the lead masons follow the building compliance during construction.

Perspective of Mason for the Reason behind non-compliance

Perspective	Percentage
Compliance	15.38
Non-Compliance- Modify the design to make work easy	15.38
Non-Compliance- Modify the design as instructed by owners	69.23

F. Reasons behind the Non-Compliance and Probable Solutions

Key Informant Interview (KII) was conducted with the Chairperson, Vice-chairperson, Chief Administrative Officer and Technical Personnel of Rural Municipality who are involved in building permit related works in the municipality. The unstructured interviewing method was used to collect at least three reasons and three probable solutions to overcome the problem. The details are discussed here after

1) View of Chair Person and Vice Chairperson

a) Reasons behind Non-Compliance

- Lack of Awareness of general public and house owner on code compliance as this is very new subject to them
- Lack of sufficient training to technical manpower in the municipality for timely and frequent supervision
- Lack of availability of trained masons and contractor in Sisne Rural Municipality

b) Probable Solutions

- Rural municipal should conduct mass awareness programme on need of earthquake resistant design and application of building code for the general public and house owner

- Rural municipal should conduct sufficient training to their in-house technical personnel.

- Rural Municipality should start to train the available mason in Sisne Rural Municipality

2) View of Chief Administrative Officer

a) Reasons behind Non-Compliance

- Lack of effective process of building permit and standard operating procedures for controlling code compliance during construction.

- Lack of coordination between the house owner, designer and masons involved in construction

- Misconception of the house owner that the compliance of code will increase the cost of the building

b) Probable Solutions

- Preparation and enactment of standard operating procedures for effective building permit process to enhance the code compliance during construction.

- Awareness to House owner during the approval of the building permit on compliance requirement of building code

- Introducing three party agreement processes between the owner, designer and mason involved in the construction for better coordination.

3) View of Municipal Technical Personnel

a) Reasons behind Non-Compliance

- Lack of availability of trained masons to understand the drawings and earthquake resistant construction in Sisne Rural Municipality

- Lack of sufficient practical knowledge among sub-engineers and lack of stringent monitoring and supervision

- House owners usually believe in contractor/mason than designer/engineer and most of them think that the approval of drawings is just a matter of procedure to get permission from Rural Municipality which they can alter and modify according to their own needs during construction.

b) *Probable Solutions*

- Preparation and enactment of Enactment of an effective reward and punishment system for compliance and non-compliance through stringent monitoring and supervision during construction.

- Sufficient training to the sub-engineers about practical knowledge on code compliance during construction.

- Intensive awareness to the house owners and training to the available masons in Sisne Rural Municipality to overcome the confusion and misconception.

VI. Conclusion

The study was focused on determining compliance of building code in construction of residential buildings in Sisne Rural Municipality. The methodology used was study of secondary data, field observation, questionnaires survey, and key informant interviews. Based on the research findings, the following conclusions were drawn.

The study showed that the out of 27 constructed buildings only one building was comply with the checklist of compliance and remaining buildings are not complied. It has been found that various parameters like changes in plinth area, size of room, change in depth of beam and change in size and position of staircase have been altered than approved design and drawings.

Similarly, out of 13 under construction buildings, none of the buildings are comply as per the compliance checklist. The analysis showed that lapping of column rebar, lapping of beam rebar are major lacking during the construction. 100% of building under construction do not comply with lapping of rebar on column and 28% of ongoing construction fails to meet compliance on lapping of top and bottom rebar on beam

The study shows that awareness levels of the masons under consideration have not sufficient level of awareness on basic concept behind the compliance of the building code. Majority of them were unaware about the earthquake and its phenomenon, have no awareness about the general concept on the earthquake resistant design and construction of the buildings,

building code and its provisions and the process of approval of drawings from Rural Municipality. The study also shows that capabilities of the masons working in Sisne Rural Municipality for construction of building was not satisfactory. All of the lead Masons were found untrained masons who and are not fully capable to follow various aspects of the building code and its compliance during construction.

The perspective of masons for the reasons behind non-compliance of building code is adaptation of construction practice that violated the compliance of code in construction due to instructions from owner during construction. There has also been noticed that masons too alter the drawings to make easy in construction violating the compliance requirement.

From the study it has been found that the major reasons behind non-compliance in construction are due to lack of awareness of general public and house owner on code compliance as this is very new subject to them, lack of sufficient training to technical manpower in the municipality for timely and frequent supervision, lack of availability of trained masons and contractor in Sisne Rural Municipality, lack of effective process of building permit and standard operating procedures for controlling code compliance during construction, lack of coordination between the house owner, designer and masons involved in construction, misconception of the house owner that the compliance of code will increase the cost of the building, lack of sufficient practical knowledge among sub-engineers and lack of stringent monitoring and supervision and disbelief of house owners.

VII. Recommendation from study

The study recommends the probable solutions to overcome the problems of non-compliance as conduction of mass awareness programme on need of earthquake resistant design and application of building code for the general public and house owner, sufficient training to their in-house technical personnel, municipality start to train the available mason in Sisne Rural Municipality, prepare and enact standard operating procedures for effective building permit process to enhance the code compliance during construction, introducing three party agreement processes between the owner, designer and mason involved in the construction for better coordination, preparer and enact effective reward and punishment system for compliance and non-compliance through stringent monitoring and supervision during construction.

Sisne Rural Municipality is recommended to formulate building construction and supervision guideline and the visit of technical team should strictly implement the guideline.

Comprehensive study with on field material and lab testing (both destructive and non-destructive) is recommended to understand the change in strength and seismic resistance capacity of building resulted due to not following the construction compliance.

VIII. Recommendation for further study

- i. Similar studies should be conducted in other municipalities and rural municipalities in Nepal.
- ii. Study of compliance of code focused on construction quality should be carried out
- iii. Similar study on steel structures should be conducted
- iv. Comparison of steel structures and RCC structures in compliance of building code should be carried out

ACKNOWLEDGMENT

We would specially like to thank and acknowledge to the elected members and officials of Sisne Rural Municipality.

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